

OntoFoCE and ObE Forensics. Email-traceability supporting tools for Digital Forensics
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Supplementary material: BIBLIOGRAPHIC SURVEY 2019- FIRST QUARTER 2023

The publication [Parra, 2019] describes the bibliographic review done at the beginning of the research, focused on the search for relevant publications between 2014 and 2018. Using the same methodology and sources of information, we searched for relevant publications between 2019 and the first half of 2023. For this second literature review, the publications of interest are shown in Table 1. Two search criteria were used:

- Search Criteria 1: ontology AND forensic AND email AND year>=2019 AND year<=2023
- Search Criteria 2: forensic AND header email AND year>=2019 AND year<=2023

Table 1: Bibliographic Survey 2019-First Quarter 2023

Id.	Journal	Year	Title	Authors	Abstract	Cite as
1	IEEE Xplore	2019	A Comprehensive Survey for Intelligent Spam Email Detection	Karim, A., Azam, S. , Shanmugam, B. , Kannoopatti, K., Alazab, M.	This survey paper describes a focused literature survey of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) methods for intelligent spam email detection.	[Karim et al., 2019]
2	IEEE Xplore	2019	Ontology for Reactive Techniques in Digital Forensics	Ellison, D., Ikuesan, R. A., Venter, H. S.	An ontology representing digital forensic reactive techniques classified by function (or action in terms of a verb) is presented, contributing to an essentially useful knowledge base as a resource for those operating in the field of digital forensics.	[Ellison, 2020]
3	IEEE Xplore	2019	Recognizing Email Spam from Meta Data Only	Krause, T., Uetz, R., Kretschmann, T.	We propose a new spam detection approach based solely on meta data features gained from email headers.	[Krause et al., 2019]
4	IEEE Xplore	2020	Blocking Phishing e-mail by extracting header information of e-mails	Surwade, A.U.	This paper has described development of filter based on origin-based information of e-mail called as Origin based Filter which blocks these phishing e-mails at MTA or MDA level by extracting header part information of these e-mails using Blacklist approach.	[Surwade, 2020]
5	IEEE Xplore	2021	Evading DoH via Live Memory Forensics for Phishing Detection and Content Filtering	Varshney, G., Iyer, P., Atrey, P., Misra M.	In this paper, we propose a novel idea to uncover the DoH traffic by directly sniffing URLs from the RAM of end points/client machines. Our approach can be used by an organization's content filtering and phishing detection solutions.	[Varshney et al., 2021]
6	Scholar Google	2020	A description logic ontology for email phishing	Tchakounté, F., Molengar, D., & Ngossaha, J. M.	This paper addresses this problem by proposing a formalized description logic to build the knowledge base of phishing attacks. In addition, it designs an ontology-oriented approach to add semantics to that knowledge.	[Tchakounté et al., 2020]
7	Scholar Google	2020	Development of Ontology on Crime Investigation process	Srimukh, P., Shridevi, S.	This paper is an extended version of the research paper "Ontology based crime investigation process" which deals with the working principle and the construction of an ontology based extensively on organized crime. Ontologies on various domains are created in which their assistance has been widely recognized.	[Srimukh & Shridevi, 2020]

Id.	Journal	Year	Title	Authors	Abstract	Cite as
8	Scholar Google	2020	Ontology-driven perspective of CFRaaS	Kebande, V., Karie, N., Ikuesan, R., Venter, H.	A Cloud Forensic Readiness as a Service (CFRaaS) model allows an environment to preemptively accumulate relevant potential digital evidence (PDE) which may be needed during a post-event response process. The article presents the CFRaaS from a holistic ontology-driven perspective	[Kebande et al., 2020]
9	Scholar Google	2020	SankeyVis: Visualizing active relationship from emails based on multiple dimensions and topic classification methods	Fang, Y., Zhao, C., Huang, C., & Liu, L.	This paper proposed SankeyVis: a visualization model for email forensics of active relation based on multiple dimensions and LDA topic classification methods, focusing on mining social relationships and semantic patterns in emails. SankeyVis conducts forensic work from the four data attributes of the email, "From," "To," "Date," and "Body," and the data is divided into two parts, the email header and email body according to the structure. The email header is used to get address pair with the working relationship after selecting and for the email body.	[Fang et al., 2020]
10	Scholar Google	2021	AI in digital forensics: Ontology engineering for cybercrime investigations	Sikos, L. F.	This article offers a review of ontologies addressing unstructured forensic data derived from various sources and ontologies that formally describe digital forensics and investigates its applicability in automating digital evidence trail processing.	[Sikos, 2021]
11	Scholar Google	2021	Forensic Analysis of E-mail for Authorship Attribution: Research Perspective	Apoorva, K. A., Sangeetha, S.	This paper emphasis such varied algorithms and justifies the efficient use of the support vector machine algorithm for forensic analysis of data and also provides the related works and techniques for author attribution	[Apoorva & Sangeetha, 2020]
12	Scholar Google	2022	A forensic-driven data model for automatic vehicles events analysis	Akremi, A.	Este documento utiliza técnicas basadas en la semántica para modelar el flujo de datos entre las cámaras, los puntos de control y los administradores, ayudando en la búsqueda y correlación automática de eventos para rastrear vehículos sospechosos de manera eficiente.	[Akremi, 2022]
13	Scholar Google	2022	Fronesis: Digital Forensics-Based Early Detection of Ongoing Cyber-Attacks	Dimitriadis, A., Lontzetidis, E., Kulvatunyou, B., Ivezic, N., Gritzalis, D., & Mavridis, I.	Este documento presenta un enfoque para la detección temprana basada en análisis forense digital de ciberataques llamados Fronesis. El enfoque combina el razonamiento ontológico con MITRE ATT&CK marco, el modelo Cyber Kill Chain y los artefactos digitales adquiridos continuamente del monitoreo sistema informático	[Dimitriadis et al., 2022]
14	Scholar Google	2023	A Unified Forensics Analysis Approach to Digital Investigation	Alshumrani, A., Clarke, N., & Ghita, B.	This research paper investigates the limitations of the current state of the art in the digital forensics discipline and categories common investigation crimes with the necessary corresponding digital analyses to define the characteristics of the next-generation approach	[Alshumrani et al., 2023]

Id.	Journal	Year	Title	Authors	Abstract	Cite as
15	ScienceDirect	2019	A new semantic-based feature selection method for spam filtering	Méndez, J., Cotos-Yañez, T., Ruano-Ordás, D.	This study deals with the massive delivery of unwanted content or advertising campaigns without the accordance of target users (also known as spam). Currently, words (tokens) are selected by using feature selection schemes; they are then used to create feature vectors for training different Machine Learning (ML) approaches	[Méndez et al., 2019]
16	ScienceDirect	2019	Machine learning for email spam filtering: review, approaches and open research problems	Dada, E. G., Bassi, J. S., Chiroma, H., Adetunmbi, A. O., & Ajibuwa, O. E.	We present a systematic review of some of the popular machine learning based email spam filtering approaches. Our review covers survey of the important concepts, attempts, efficiency, and the research trend in spam filtering.	[Dada et al., 2019]
17	ScienceDirect	2019	Spam e-mail detection using advanced deep convolution neural network algorithms	Soni, A.	In this paper, we initially examined the email structure. At that point, in light of an improved intermittent convolutional neural systems (RCNN) model with staggered vectors and consideration instrument, we proposed another Spam e-mail recognition model named THEMIS, which is utilized to show emails at the email header, the email body, the character level, and the word level all the while	[Soni, 2020]
18	ScienceDirect	2020	A Semantic Engine and an Ontology Visualization Tool for Advanced Crime Analysis	Peppes, N., Alexakis, T., Adamopoulou, E., Remoundou, K., Demestichas, K.	This paper focuses on two specific functionalities of a crime prediction and fighting software framework which assists LEAs to adopt and utilize emerging technologies such as Data mining and Big Data tools, Semantic Analysis, Visual Intelligence and more in the context of their everyday operations	[Peppes et al., 2020]
19	ScienceDirect	2020	A semantic-based classification approach for an enhanced spam detection	Saidani, N., Adi, K., Allili, M.	In this paper, we explore the use of a text semantic analysis to improve the accuracy of spam detection. We propose a method based on two semantic level analysis. In the first level, we categorize emails by specific domains (e.g., Health, Education, Finance, etc.) to enable a separate conceptual view for spams in each domain. In the second level, we combine a set of manually specified and automatically extracted semantic features for spam detection in each domain.	[Saidani et al., 2020]
20	ScienceDirect	2020	Formal knowledge model for online social network forensics	Arshad, H., Jantan, A., Hoon, G., Abiodun, I.	This model consists of an event-based knowledge model, which provides theoretical concepts that can assist in the construction and interpretation of the events related to the incident under investigation. The proposed model is implemented through an ontology to provide semantically rich and formal representation to the concepts. This article also describes the feasibility of legally acceptable automated analysis operators, based on a formal theory, for online social network forensics.	[Arshad et al., 2020]
21	ScienceDirect	2021	SeFACED: Semantic-Based Forensic Analysis and	Hina, M., Ali, M. , Javed, A. R., Ghabban, F. , Khan, L. A., Jalil, Z.	To investigate crimes involving Electronic Mail (e-mail), analysis of both the header and the email body is required since the semantics of communication helps to identify the source of potential evidence.	[Hina et al., 2021]

Id.	Journal	Year	Title	Authors	Abstract	Cite as
			Classification of E-Mail Data Using Deep Learning		we propose a novel efficient approach named SeFACED that uses Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) based Gated Recurrent Neural Network (GRU) for multiclass email classification	
22	ScienceDirect	2023	A comprehensive survey on deep learning-based malware detection techniques	Gopinath M., Sibi Chakkaravarthy Sethuraman	Comprehensive analysis of newly developed DL-based malware detection techniques. In addition, current trending malwares are studied and detection techniques for mobile malware (Android and iOS), Windows malware, IoT malware, advanced persistent threats (APT) and Ransomware are accurately reviewed.	[Gopinath et al., 2022]
23	ScienceDirect	2023	An ontology-driven framework for knowledge representation of digital extortion attacks	Keshavarzi, M., Ghaffary, H.R.	The complexity and multiplicity of components involved in digital extortion implies the construction of a knowledge representation system that is capable of organizing large volumes of information from heterogeneous sources in a formal structured format and inferring new knowledge from it. This paper suggests and develops a dedicated digital blackmail ontology, called Rantology, with a particular focus on ransomware attacks.	[Keshavarzi & Ghaffary, 2023]
24	ScienceDirect	2023	Interpol review of digital evidence for 2019–2022	Reedy, P.	Bibliographic review that cites approximately 260 references that were published from the end of 2019 to the most recent before November 2022, presents the progress and maturation of Digital Forensia, detailing types of crimes, tools and methodologies that emerged in the indicated period, marking the role that ontological engineering contributes in the case of methodologies based on ontologies, analysis of file systems, reconstruction of events, taxonomy of data of an Android device and in the development of a database on forensic cases.	[Reedy, 2023]
25	Scopus	2019	Phishing attacks in Qatar: A literature review of the problems and solutions	Al-Hamar Y., Kolivand H., Al-Hamar A.	This paper outlines the literature on phishing attacks in Qatar and techniques for countering them. It begins with the background of phishing, specifically spear phishing, in Qatar and the urgency of the issue. Then, it presents some of the literature and research on anti-phishing techniques. There are several technical solutions proposed in the literature to detect and defend email phishing attacks, however, these techniques cannot detect and stop genuinely looking phishing emails	[Al-Hamar et al., 2019]
26	Scopus	2019	Technology assisted analysis of timeline and connections in digital forensic investigations	Henseler, H., & Hyde, J.	This article describes ongoing research on the application of AI techniques such as Graph Neural Networks to assist investigators with the discovery of relations and patterns in digital forensic evidence.	[Henseler & Hyde, 2019]
27	Scopus	2020	Identification of Spoofed Emails by applying Email Forensics and Memory Forensics	Shukla, S., Misra, M., & Varshney, G.	In our work, we detect spoofed emails received by the user by applying memory forensic approach. Instead of capturing the complete memory dump, we only capture the browser's live running processes from memory and extract the email header for analysis	[Shukla et al., 2020]

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